

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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**RESTORATIVE CONSIDERATIONS FOR ENDODONTICALLY TREATED TEETH:
STRUCTURAL AND CLINICAL ASPECTS****Kim V.E.**

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Resume. The restoration of endodontically treated teeth (ETT) remains one of the most extensively studied yet debated subjects in restorative dentistry. Despite considerable research, questions persist regarding the optimal clinical protocols and materials to be employed, particularly since fractures are frequently associated with these teeth. To address these concerns, a comprehensive search of the MEDLINE/PubMed database was conducted, focusing on studies published over the past decade. The search strategy included the following keywords: nonvital teeth, endodontically treated teeth, pulpless teeth, devitalized teeth, dental restoration, dental pins, dental post, root canal preparation, and post-and-core technique. This search yielded 207 studies, of which 43 were selected for inclusion in this review. The selection was based on their relevance to fracture resistance in endodontically treated teeth restored using different approaches and restorative materials.

Key words: teeth, endodontics, restorative dentistry

**ЭНДОДОНТИК ДАВОЛАНГАН ТИШЛАРНИ РЕСТАВРАЦИЯ ҚИЛИШДАГИ
ЁНДАШУВЛАР: ТУЗИЛМАВИЙ ВА КЛИНИК ЖИХАТЛАР****Ким В.Э.**

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Резюме. Эндодонтик даволанган тишларни (ETT) тиклаш реставрацион стоматологияда энг кўп ўрганган, бироқ баҳсли мавзулардан бири бўлиб қолмоқда. Кўплаб тадқиқотлар мавжуд бўлишига қарамай, оптимал клиник протоколлар ва қўлланиладиган материалларни танлаш бўйича саволлар сақланиб қолмоқда, айниқса, бундай тишларда синиш ҳолатлари тез-тез учраши сабабли. Ушбу масалаларни ўрганиш мақсадида сўнги ўн йил ичида чоп этилган тадқиқотларга эътибор қаратилган ҳолда MEDLINE/PubMed маълумотлар базасида кенг қамровли қидирув ўтказилди. Қидирув стратегияси қўйидаги калит сўзларни ўз ичига олди: нонвитал тишлар, эндодонтик даволанган тишлар, пульпасиз тишлар, девитализация қилинган тишлар, стоматологик реставрация, стоматологик пинлар, стоматологик штифт, илдиз каналли тайёрлаш ва штифт-культя техникаси. Қидирув натижасида 207 та тадқиқот аниқланди, шулардан 43 таси ушбу шарҳга киритилиш учун танлаб олинди. Танлов турли ёндашувлар ва реставрацион материаллар ёрдамида тикланган эндодонтик даволанган тишларнинг синишига чидамлилигига оид аҳамияти асосида амалга оширилди.

Калит сўзлар: тишлар, эндодонтия, реставрацион стоматология

**РЕСТАВРАЦИОННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЭНДОДОНТИЧЕСКИ ЛЕЧЕННЫХ ЗУБОВ:
СТРУКТУРНЫЕ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ****Ким В.Э.**

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Резюме. Восстановление эндодонтически леченных зубов (ETT) остаётся одной из наиболее изучаемых и одновременно дискуссионных тем в реставрационной стоматологии. Несмотря на большое количество исследований, вопросы выбора оптимальных клинических протоколов и материалов остаются актуальными, особенно в связи с высокой частотой переломов таких зубов. Для анализа данной проблемы был проведён поиск в базе данных MEDLINE/PubMed по исследованиям, опубликованным за последнее десятилетие. Поисковая стратегия включала ключевые слова: неживые зубы, эндодонтически леченные зубы, депульпированные зубы, девитализированные зубы, стоматологическая реставрация, стоматологические штифты, внутрикорневые штифты, подготовка корневого канала и техника штифтово-культевой реставрации. В результате было найдено 207 исследований, из которых 43 включены в данный обзор на основании их значимости в оценке устойчивости к перелому эндодонтически леченных зубов, восстановленных различными методами и материалами.

Ключевые слова: зубы, эндодонтия, реставрационная стоматология

Characteristics of Endodontically Treated Teeth. Fractures are reported more frequently in pulpless teeth compared to teeth with vital pulps [1]. However, some studies indicate only a modest difference in fracture incidence between non-endodontically treated teeth (41%) and endodontically treated teeth (58%) among Chinese patients. Interestingly, the higher fracture rate in non-treated teeth within this population was attributed to specific dietary habits, such as chewing bones in meat, which may increase occlusal stress [2]. Additional variables, including sex, age, and dental arch, also appear to influence fracture prevalence [3]. For instance, Chan et al. [2] observed that fractures were 1.4 times more common in men than in women, with peak incidence occurring between 40 and 49 years of age in men and between 50 and 59 years in women.

To better understand the underlying causes of fractures in endodontically treated teeth, early research focused on the role of dentin alterations. Helfer et al. [4] suggested in 1972 that pulpless teeth lose approximately 10% of their water content, potentially affecting their biomechanical properties. Nevertheless, subsequent investigations evaluating dentin parameters such as microhardness, elastic modulus, and tensile/compressive strength demonstrated only minor changes between vital and pulpless teeth, insufficient to significantly compromise fracture resistance, although slight differences in moisture content and dentin properties were noted [5–7].

Historically, endodontically treated teeth were considered more brittle due to structural modifications of dentin, including reduced water content and diminished collagen cross-linking following root canal therapy [8]. Current evidence, however, emphasizes that the primary factor contributing to increased fracture susceptibility is the loss of structural integrity. This arises mainly from extensive caries, pre-existing restorations, and access cavity preparation, which collectively weaken the tooth and increase cuspal deflection during function [1,9]. Thus, it is challenging to differentiate whether fracture risk is mainly due to intrinsic changes in dentin or the cumulative loss of coronal structure.

Another critical issue affecting endodontically treated teeth is coronal microleakage and subsequent bacterial contamination when definitive restorations are delayed. This condition can result in endodontic failure and the need for retreatment [10]. To mitigate this risk, bonded restorative techniques are recommended as they provide improved sealing ability and reduce microleakage.

Treatment Planning. Despite the extensive research conducted on endodontically treated teeth, the optimal treatment planning and restorative materials remain a subject of debate. The complexity of decision-making in this field is illustrated by a study reported by Türp et al. [11], in which four dental specialists were asked to provide treatment strategies for a fractured lateral incisor. Notably, each specialist proposed a different approach, reflecting the diversity of perspectives found in the literature.

This variability highlights the ongoing uncertainty among clinicians regarding the most appropriate restorative method—whether to employ direct or indirect restorations, to incorporate posts or not, and which restorative materials and preparation principles should be prioritized.

When planning treatment, several criteria must be taken into consideration. The amount of residual coronal tooth structure is a decisive factor, as it directly influences the choice of restoration type. Additionally, the functional requirements of the restored tooth—such as occlusal load and position within the dental arch—must be carefully assessed. Together, these parameters provide the foundation for selecting both the restorative material and the technique that will best ensure long-term clinical success.

Functional Requirements. The functional demands placed on endodontically treated teeth vary depending on their position within the dental arch, and this factor should be carefully considered when selecting restorative materials and techniques. Occlusal forces differ significantly between anterior and posterior regions, influencing both the risk of fracture and the need for specific restorative strategies.

Clinical studies have demonstrated that mandibular first molars exhibit more than twice the incidence of fractures compared with maxillary first molars, premolars, and mandibular second molars [2]. This increased susceptibility has been attributed to the combination of higher masticatory loads in this region and the relatively thin or flat root morphology characteristic of mandibular first molars. Similarly, Tamse et al. [12] reported that longitudinal root fractures are more prevalent in teeth with narrow mesiodistal dimensions, particularly the maxillary premolars.

Chan et al. [2] further noted that canines tend to be the most resistant to fracture, while incisors become more vulnerable following endodontic treatment. These observations emphasize the influence of occlusal force distribution on tooth integrity. Posterior teeth primarily withstand vertical loading forces, whereas anterior teeth must resist lateral and shearing stresses. Consequently, the placement of posts is often indicated in anterior teeth to improve stress distribution across the coronal and radicular portions, thereby reducing the risk of structural failure [2,13].

Remaining Tooth Structure. The extent of residual coronal tooth structure plays a decisive role in treatment planning for endodontically treated teeth. When tooth structure loss exceeds 50% (Fig. 1), the use of intraradicular posts is generally indicated to retain a core and ensure proper stress distribution. It is important to emphasize that, contrary to earlier misconceptions, posts do not reinforce or strengthen endodontically treated teeth; rather, they serve solely to provide retention for the core in cases where significant coronal loss is present (Fig. 1A).

A strong correlation exists between the amount of remaining tooth structure and fracture resistance. Nagasiri and Chitmongkolsuk [14] reported that teeth with greater residual coronal tissue demonstrate superior long-term survival, with molars retaining substantial structure after endodontic therapy showing a 78% survival rate over a 5-year period. Similarly, Costa et al. [15] observed that cusp fractures in endodontically treated maxillary premolars were closely associated with the width of cavity preparation. Their findings indicated that increased mesio-occluso-distal (MOD) preparation width reduced fracture resistance, whereas the use of onlay restorations incorporating cusp coverage significantly improved it.

In a laboratory investigation, Steele and Johnson [16] compared fracture resistance of maxillary premolars with various preparation designs and restorative approaches. Their results showed that teeth with only endodontic access cavities preserved exhibited higher resistance to fracture than those subjected to extensive preparations, underscoring the importance of conservative tooth structure preservation whenever possible.

Restoration design and material choice play a critical role in reinforcing endodontically treated teeth. Studies have shown that teeth restored with amalgam or composite resin exhibit greater fracture resistance than unrestored teeth, regardless of the use of bonding agents. Cerutti et al. [17], in an investigation of cuspal deflection, demonstrated that endodontically treated teeth restored with amalgam recovered only about 17% of cuspal stiffness, whereas those restored with composite resin recovered between 54% and 99%, depending on the specific material employed. This highlights the superior reinforcing potential of adhesive restorative systems compared to traditional amalgam.

Cuspal Coverage. The presence or absence of cuspal coverage significantly influences the fracture resistance of endodontically treated teeth. One study demonstrated that teeth restored with crowns exhibited a sixfold higher success rate compared to uncrowned teeth, after controlling for tooth type and the presence of caries at access preparation [20]. Although alternative restorative options—such as gold, ceramic, or composite resin onlays—may also provide cuspal protection, there is insufficient clinical evidence to recommend their use for posterior teeth.

The necessity of full-coverage restorations has been debated, particularly in cases restored with fiber posts and composites. Some authors reported no additional advantage of using metal-ceramic crowns in such cases, noting that endodontically treated premolars with Class II carious lesions and preserved cusps restored with fiber posts and direct composite restorations achieved comparable clinical success to those restored with full metal-ceramic crowns over a 3-year observation period [11].

The choice of crown material also plays a role in long-term outcomes. A comparative study reported survival rates of 91.7% for cast restorations, 86.5% for amalgam restorations, and 83% for composite restorations [12]. These findings suggest that while full-coverage crowns generally enhance fracture resistance, the ultimate decision should be based on functional demands and the quantity of remaining tooth structure. Notably, teeth with preserved cusps may still demonstrate satisfactory resistance to fracture without the need for full coverage.

Use of Posts. Historically, posts were thought to reinforce endodontically treated teeth. However, current evidence indicates that preparation of a post space actually increases the risk of root fracture [13]. Consequently, posts should be employed only when essential for retaining a core, and not as a means of strengthening the tooth [1].

The decision to use a post is primarily determined by the quantity of remaining coronal tooth structure and the functional demands placed on the restoration [8,14]. Comparative studies assessing fracture resistance in teeth restored with and without posts highlight that post selection should be case-specific.

Among available options, posts can be classified as metallic, ceramic, or prefabricated (metal, glass fiber, or carbon fiber). Fiber posts, when combined with direct resin restorations, have been advocated as a conservative and time-efficient approach that preserves remaining tooth structure. Grandini et al. [15] demonstrated satisfactory clinical outcomes for fiber post-resin restorations at 6-, 12-, 24-, and 30-month follow-ups, although no direct comparison was made with teeth restored without posts.

In another study, endodontically treated teeth restored with fiber posts and composite resin exhibited superior performance in reducing root fractures compared to amalgam restorations; however, they were less effective in preventing secondary caries [16].

The mechanical properties of posts play a critical role in treatment success. Glass fiber and carbon fi-

ber posts are particularly advantageous in cases with limited radicular tooth structure, as their modulus of elasticity closely approximates that of dentin. This biomechanical compatibility allows for more uniform stress distribution within the root, thereby reducing the risk of catastrophic failure. Fredriksson et al. [17], in a clinical evaluation of carbon fiber posts, observed no root or post fractures and no dislodgement over the study period, supporting the clinical viability of this system as an alternative to conventional metallic posts.

Esthetic Considerations and Failure Modes of Fiber Posts. Although carbon fiber posts demonstrated favorable biomechanical properties, their dark color posed esthetic limitations, particularly in anterior teeth. To address this drawback, modifications such as mineral coatings were introduced to enhance their appearance. In clinical situations where esthetics is a primary concern, ceramic and glass fiber posts are generally preferred [18]. Case reports underscore the importance of using such posts in anterior teeth, where cosmetic outcomes are often a determining factor for treatment success.

Martelli [19] described the development of carbon-based and glass fiber posts with translucency and elasticity moduli closely approximating those of dentin, thereby improving both esthetics and biomechanical compatibility. In a prospective clinical follow-up study, Malferrari et al. [20] evaluated quartz fiber-reinforced epoxy posts (“Aesthetic posts”) over a 30-month period. The reported failure rate was only 1.7%, and importantly, none of the failures involved root fractures. Instead, the failures were limited to a cohesive fracture at the composite core margin and two adhesive failures due to cement–post–core detachment from the dentinal walls, all of which were manageable and successfully retreated.

These findings highlight a key difference between fiber and conventional metallic cast posts. While fiber posts most commonly fail due to displacement, detachment, or prosthesis decementation, metal cast posts tend to cause catastrophic root fractures. This is attributed to their high rigidity, which transmits lateral forces as high-frequency vibrations that can induce longitudinal root fractures when critical stress levels are reached [13].

Fiber posts, by contrast, have an elastic modulus similar to that of dentin, resulting in more favorable stress distribution. Nevertheless, adhesive failures may still occur, often due to technical inaccuracies during the cementation procedure. Another drawback is that prefabricated fiber posts typically require a thicker cement layer compared to custom-cast posts, potentially compromising retention. To overcome this, Boudrias et al. [14] proposed a double-tapered post system designed to better adapt to the anatomy of the root canal, thereby minimizing the need for excessive dentin removal, enhancing apical and coronal adaptation, and improving post retention.

Custom versus Prefabricated Posts. A clinical case report described the use of a bondable polyethylene ribbon as an alternative to conventional post-and-core build-up materials. This technique offered several advantages, including favorable esthetic properties, mechanical performance, and a neutral color of the reinforcing material. Furthermore, because the canal required minimal enlargement, the risk of apical or lateral root perforation was reduced [12]. Prefabricated posts in general offer additional benefits, such as the ability to restore teeth with minimal remaining coronal structure in a single appointment, thereby simplifying treatment planning while achieving esthetically acceptable outcomes [3,4].

The comparison between custom and prefabricated posts has been extensively studied. Fokkinga et al. [15] evaluated the fracture resistance of endodontically treated teeth restored with prefabricated metallic posts, prefabricated glass fiber posts, and custom-made glass fiber posts compared with teeth restored without posts. The study found no significant differences in fracture resistance or failure modes among the groups. Similar findings were reported by other researchers [6,12], who assessed different post designs in the context of fixed prosthetic rehabilitation.

However, fracture patterns appear to vary depending on the type of post and loading conditions. Hayashi et al. [18] demonstrated that teeth restored with cast metallic post–cores exhibited higher resistance under vertical loading, whereas prefabricated metallic posts required less force to fail under oblique loading. Importantly, the mode of failure differed: vertical loading typically caused cracks propagating through the middle or apical third of the roots, while oblique loading led to cervical root fractures with fiber posts and middle-root fractures with prefabricated or cast metallic post–cores. Although cast metallic posts provide greater absolute fracture resistance, failures in these cases are often catastrophic and render the tooth unrestorable. In contrast, cervical root fractures associated with fiber posts may still allow for retreatment and tooth preservation.

Long-term clinical data further support the use of fiber posts. Glazer [19] reported on a 5-year clinical follow-up of patients whose remaining coronal tooth structure was less than 50%. Teeth restored with carbon fiber posts and metal-ceramic crowns demonstrated an overall failure rate of 7.7% and a cumulative survival rate of 89.6%. Success rates were higher in maxillary anterior teeth compared with premolars, particularly mandibular premolars, likely due to the narrow mesiodistal root dimensions in the latter. These results high-

light the importance of considering occlusal dynamics when selecting a post system, since canines and maxillary incisors, which guide disocclusion and incise food, are subjected to significant oblique loading, often necessitating the use of posts for reinforcement.

Clinical evaluations over a 6-year period of three fiber post systems (840 Composipost, 215 Aesthetic posts, and 249 Aesthetic Plus posts), combined with four types of resin cements, confirmed that fiber posts can be routinely used in conjunction with adhesive agents to provide reliable outcomes [20].

Ultimately, post selection should align with the overall rehabilitation strategy. Teeth serving as abutments for fixed partial dentures are subjected to higher functional demands compared with teeth restored with single crowns. For such cases, ceramic or metallic custom posts are often recommended, despite the need for greater canal enlargement during post space preparation [11]. These systems also facilitate proper alignment among abutment teeth. In contrast, when endodontically treated teeth were evaluated as abutments, success rates were notably higher for fixed partial dentures (92.7%) compared with removable partial dentures (51%), as reported by Wegner et al. [12].

Discussion. The restoration of endodontically treated teeth (ETT) requires careful consideration of multiple factors, including the extent of remaining tooth structure, functional demands, and the properties of restorative materials. When tooth loss is minimal and preparation is limited to endodontic access, conservative approaches such as direct restorations with amalgam or composite resin combined with adhesive systems can provide satisfactory outcomes and reduce the risk of microleakage.

In contrast, posterior teeth with substantial structural loss often require cuspal coverage to redirect occlusal forces along the long axis of the root, thereby reducing the likelihood of vertical root fractures. Anterior teeth, however, are more frequently exposed to oblique forces, which often necessitate the placement of posts for adequate reinforcement and retention. While posts are primarily indicated to retain a core in cases of extensive coronal loss (Fig. 1), some studies have proposed combining posts with composite restorations as an alternative to full-coverage crowns in posterior teeth.

The selection of a post system is complex, given the wide range of available options, including metallic, ceramic, and fiber posts, which may be prefabricated or custom-made. Fiber posts are generally recommended in cases with compromised root structure due to their elastic modulus being close to that of dentin, which allows for more favorable stress distribution. However, adequate coronal structure must remain to ensure proper retention of the core through adhesive bonding. By contrast, cast metallic posts are preferred in situations of extensive coronal loss (Fig. 1) or in teeth subjected to higher functional demands, such as abutments for removable or fixed partial prostheses.

The selection of an appropriate post should adhere to several biomechanical and clinical principles: preservation of tooth structure, retention and resistance, retrievability, the presence of a ferrule, and the expected failure mode [3,13]. Whenever possible, preparation of the post space should minimize removal of both coronal and radicular dentin. Retention depends on post geometry (length, diameter, and taper), surface characteristics, luting agent, and degree of passivity, though clinicians typically have control only over the geometric parameters. Resistance is largely influenced by the remaining coronal structure, which enhances the post-tooth complex's ability to resist lateral and rotational stresses while distributing occlusal loads effectively. Retrievability is another critical factor, especially in the event of retreatment. Finally, failure patterns differ by post type: fiber posts often fail through debonding or displacement, which are usually repairable, whereas cast metal posts are more frequently associated with catastrophic root fractures that preclude further restoration.

Conclusion. Endodontically treated teeth are inherently more prone to biomechanical failure, not only because of structural alterations in the dentin but, more importantly, due to the cumulative loss of coronal and radicular tooth substance resulting from caries, prior restorations, and endodontic access preparation. As a result, the restorative strategy should be carefully individualized, taking into consideration both the extent of the remaining tooth structure and the functional requirements of the tooth. When a substantial portion of coronal structure remains, conservative adhesive restorations may provide sufficient reinforcement. In contrast, teeth with significant structural loss frequently require cuspal coverage or the placement of posts to retain a core and distribute functional stresses. Moreover, tooth position within the arch, occlusal loading patterns, and the broader prosthetic rehabilitation plan must be integrated into decision-making to optimize longevity and clinical outcomes. Therefore, successful management of endodontically treated teeth depends on a balance between preservation of remaining tissues, appropriate restorative design, and the use of materials that ensure both biomechanical stability and biological compatibility.

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